

Problems and Prospects of Agri-Preneurship in India

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Abstract

An incline from agriculture to agribusiness is a crucial pathway to bring change or draw revolution in Indian cultivation and to draw more lavish and well-off venture. Agri-preneurship has the strength to fund to a chain of free to all and monetary knowledge such as work generation, poverty slump and improvements in nutrition, toughness and completely food stake in the national economy. Agri-preneurship has art to prompt growth, diversifying salary, providing widespread field and entrepreneurial opportunities in suburban areas. This freebie mainly focuses on fundamental concepts of Agri-preneurship, entrepreneurship skills, and needs of Agri-preneurship development along by all of the opportunities in this area. As Farmers are the backbone of our country there comes a need to materialize some agri-preneurs in ahead of its time scenario.

Keywords: Agri-preneurship, Opportunities, Agricultural, allied sectors.

Introduction

Entrepreneurship has been unified to amplified riches, multiplied aggressiveness of countries, increased point of departure of high on the hog and increased position of life. After wholesale liberalization, an entrepreneurial reaction is playing the biggest role in socioeconomic. In developing countries get a charge out of India for raising the income standard of the vast voting majority of the rearward regions, grand design and implementation for the society of entrepreneurial programmes are essential seeing of their over-dependence on production for work. Thus, entrepreneurship development in suburban industries looks the outstanding potential up to the person to find work avenues for the suburban population. The authority of an entrepreneurship life-style in the agricultural region and business planning for agricultural companies from input traders to producers and to processors and the steps compelled upon to explain a thorough commercial enterprises. Entrepreneurship involves seeking and exploiting opportunities at hand for the wealth of society. In this style, relish other kinds of developments, entrepreneurship development is further contextual. Entrepreneurship frame of reference modification from region to region and subsequently from time to time in the cognate region. Viewed from the above angle, the changeable agro-economic warning for far some time in our country have offered a later context for developing entrepreneurship in agri-business, called Agri-preneurship in the country.

Agri-Preneurship

Agri-preneurship is the entrepreneurial style taken up in agriculture or the allied sectors. It is the practice of adopting new methods, processes, techniques in agricultural or the allied sectors of agriculture, for transcending output and monetary earnings. Agri-preneurship converts agricultural activity into entrepreneurial activity. By adopting creative ideas in agriculture and allied sectors an agri-preneur who is an innovator drives the changes in the suburban economy. An agri-preneur service is never easy as he takes shot in the dark, adopts an innovation, creates new ways of doing materials and taps beautiful markets opportunities. Dollinger (2003) defines entrepreneurship in agriculture as “the creation of an innovative economic organization for growth or gain under conditions of risk and uncertainty in agriculture”.

Objectives of the Study

1. To study the need for developing Agri-preneurship in India.
2. To know the opportunities available in Agri-preneurship.
3. To study the major challenges faced by the Agri-preneurship.
4. To suggest some measures to develop the Agri-preneurship in India.

Need for Developing Agri-Preneurship in India

Agriculture is the spine of the Indian economy. Hence, India is also referred to as an “agriculture-dominated country”. That agriculture performs an essential role in the Indian economic system is identified through the statistics that it contributes 22 % to the whole gross home products, gives employment to round 65% of the total work force, and contributes 14.7% of entire exports of the country. The agriculture has developed over the decade is mirrored through a variety of forms such as growing productivity, cropping intensity, high-yielding range seeds, diversification, mechanization, and modernization of agriculture.

The need for and importance of Agricultural Development in the country can be imbued with a multiplicity of justifications as follows:

1. Availability of design for agriculture purpose.
2. The low need of funds for agricultural activity.
3. Illiterate and or less skilled population.
4. Lack of employment chance in the regional sector.
5. Prevalence of large-scale unemployment.
6. Both backward and forward inducements and linkages of Agricultural Development for industrial development.

An economic broadly consists of two sectors, namely, agriculture and industry. Agriculture helps to develop the rural economy because of the industry to that of the urban economy. Still, 72 percent of India’s population resides in the non-urban area and the rural areas are characteristics by widespread unemployment and abject poverty. Thus, the economic development of the rural area helps to improve the Indian economy. As regards how to develop rural economy, it depends on the development of all the sectors what opportunities and possibilities exist there. Of late, the new agro-economic conditions have contributed a good scope for the development of agribusiness especially in non-urban areas of the country. Globally agribusiness is considered to be a sunrise industry as it gives good promises by attracting huge investment including foreign investment.

Benefits of monetary improvement in agribusiness are quite a number of verities and traditions. It generates on the spot giant employment, make use of the best human or natural resources, promotes capital formation by mobilizing the ideal financial savings of the community, decreases joblessness, promotes balanced regional development, reduce attention of financial power, promotes fair distribution of wealth, profits and even political power, induces backward and ahead linkage for Industrial and monetary improvement and promotes nations exports.

Opportunities for Developing Agri-Preneurship

Now that we have justify the need for developing entrepreneurship in agribusiness to unfold the opportunities available for developing entrepreneurship in agribusiness in India. In general, and in rural areas in particular. The recent WTO have opened new visit for agriculture growth and changes and turn, agribusiness in the member countries including India. As such, growing opportunities are arisen for developing entrepreneurship in agribusiness sector especially agriculture, sericulture, floriculture, horticulture, animal husbandry and veterinary, fishery, etc.

The following table reveals the opportunities in Agribusiness,

Sector	Opportunities
Agriculture	Organic Farming
	Agro-based industry
	Farm Mechanization
	Pulse and Oilseeds, Post-Harvest and Processing
	Quality Input Production and Supply Chain
Horticulture	Organic Farming
Fruits	Commercial Production
Vegetables	Marketing
Flowers	Processing
Aromatic and Herbal	Packaging
Plantation	Off-season Vegetables and Quality Flower Production
	Commercial Flower Production
	Aromatic and Herbal Plantation
Animal Husbandry and Veterinary	Dairy Processing and Chilling
	Meat Processing
	Broiler and Egg Production and Marketing
	Livestock Feed
	Livestock Vaccine/ Drug Production
Fishery	Scientific and Commercial Production
	Integrated and Intensive Farming
	Carp Hatchery
	Ornamental Fish
	Fish Feed

Sericulture	Silkworm Rearing Technology
	Silk Yarn Production
	Handloom and Textile/ Garment Design
	Exports
Others	Mass Production of Biopesticides
	Bio-Fertilizers Production and Marketing
	Mushroom Marketing
	Vermi Compost
	Beekeeping and Honey Marketing

Challenges Involved in Developing Agri - Preneurship

Emerging entrepreneurship in agribusiness isan abundant useful is not so simpleand easy. In fact, there are several challenges, but not confined to the following only, involved in developing entrepreneurship in agribusiness.

Lack of Skilled and Managerial Manpower

Non - urban areas also suffer from rural-urban migration mainly male migration. This results in the denudation of educated and skilled workers in non-urban areas. Insufficient skilled and managerial manpower in non-urban areas is primarily due to the absence of proper educational institutions in non-urban areas. Moreover, people even otherwise belonging to non-urban areas do not want to go back to rural areas to work due to various problems the rural areas undergo from.

Lack of Infrastructural Facilities

Infrastructure facilitates performing any activity. There is a need for the availability of the least level of prior-built up infrastructural facilities to undertake any economic activity including starting an enterprise. On the other hand, especially rural areas suffer from the lack of or weak infrastructural facilities in terms of road, rail, telecommunication, electricity, market information network, etc. This, in return, adversely affects the effective use of agri-resources available, on the one hand, and efficiency and mobility of labour, on the other side of the coin.

The problem of Marketing

If proof of the pudding is placed in eating, the evidence of production centered on consumption. Production has no value unless it is sold/consumed. The major marketing problems faced by agri-entrepreneurship are lack of marketing programmes and networks, promotional facilities, support system, poor quality of products, and competition with medium and large-scale enterprises.

The enterprises run by agripreneurs often do not own any marketing organization. In consequence, their products compare unfavorably with the quality of the products made by medium and large-scale organizations.

Lack of Awareness about Career in Agri-preneurship

Assuming entrepreneurial career has not been considered respectable in the society for one reason or other. Entrepreneurship as a career has been associated with specific sections of the societies like Gujratis, Marwari's and Rajasthanis.

Although the impression about owner/business as poor has gradually been declining, yet it is still prevalent in contemporary society. Most of the people are still not aware of entrepreneurial opportunities, advantages, and its significance for the entrepreneur and society as a whole.

Inefficient or Lack of Equipments and Technologies

Today is the era of information technology and information is considered as power. Technology gives competitive advantages in various forms to compete with competitors. For example, exemplifies how technology empowers the non-urban farmers in advertising their products. But either inefficient or insufficient equipment's and technology has been one of the major problems faced by agripreneurs especially in rural areas.

Technology like satellite-based geographic information system (GIS) promises more efficient use of accessible resources and more practical management efforts, however, these technologies are lacking in most of the agri-business industries mostly in rural areas. Whereas this affects the standard of products, it conjointly makes the products costlier.

High Infrastructural and Distribution Costs

Transportation facilities are pre-requiring to create the inputs accessible at enterprise place and outputs at the placement of consumers scattered over a large territory. As most of the agri-enterprises are settled far away from urban areas, these suffer from transport problems for both inputs and outputs. As such, either there is non-availability of needed inputs and outputs at the right time at the right place or whatsoever is available is possible at a higher cost making the product ultimately costlier as compared to the products offered by enterprises at non-rural areas.

Unresponsive Government Policies

That policy enables doing matters in a very preferred and more positive way is verified by way of many industrial policies declared in our country over the period. There are pieces of proof accessible to believe that the assorted industrial policies have expedited to set the correct tone and tempo of commercial development in our country.

Realizing this, industrial policies both at small and macro levels are declared from time to time within the country. The small-scale sector has seasoned spectacular growth once the declaration of a separate industrial policy for this sector titled "Promoting and Strengthening Small, Tiny and Village enterprises, 1991."

Very recently, the Government of India has once more declared a separate industrial policy titled "Micro Small and Medium Enterprises Development (MSMED) Act, 2006. However, there has so far not been any separate policy for agribusiness in the country and in the absence of specific policy; the required development of agribusiness sector has been hampered.

Suggestion for Developing Agri-Preneurship

The proof accessible recommend that the sample scope for entrepreneurship development in agribusiness sector in India, which, however, has so far been exploited. The later suggestions facilitate to develop entrepreneurship in agribusiness in a more effective way:

- Creating awareness about Agri-preneurship
- Development of needed skilled workforce

- Development of infrastructural facilities
- Promotion and protection by the government
- Announcement of separate industrial policy
- Development of agribusiness special export zones
- Preparation of agribusiness potential reports for regions across the country.

Conclusion

In order to develop Agri-preneurship in the country, there is a need to develop required infrastructural facilities, skilled workforce, awareness about the benefits of Agri-preneurship, proper Information Network, favourable government attitude towards Agri-preneurship, separate industrial policy for agribusiness, in different parts / regions of the country. The agriculture sector encompasses a gaint potential to give to the national income while at the same time providing direct employment and income to the numerically larger and vulnerable section of the society. Agri-preneurship is not solely an opportunity but also an essential requirement for improving the production and profitability in agriculture sector.

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